

Exploring microbial dynamics in a pilot-scale microalgae raceway fed with urban wastewater: insights into the effect of operational variables

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Rebecca Nordio: Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Solaima Belachqer:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Elisa Clagnan:** Investigation, Data curation. Visualization, Writing – original draft; Ana **Sánchez Zurano:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Natalia Pichel:** Investigation, Data curation. **Emanuele Viviano:** Investigation, Data curation. **Fabrizio Adani:** Supervision and Funding acquisition. **José Luis Gúzman:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Gabriel Acién:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the H2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement (project: Digitalgaesation, 955520) and by the H2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme (projects: PRODIGIO, 101007006; REALM, 101060991). Also, this work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (project: HYCO2BIO, PID2020-112709RB-C21, TED2021-130458B-I00) and partially supported by Gruppo Ricicla – Università degli Studi di Milano - Grant number RV_RIMB16FADAN_M. All the authors would like to thank the Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training (IFAPA). S. Belachqer-EI Attar thanks the PPIT-UAL for her predoctoral research contract (CPRE2023-007).

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Abstract

Microalgae-based wastewater treatment is a promising technology efficient for nutrient recycling and biomass production. Studies continuously optimize processes to reduce costs and increase productivity. However, changes in the operational conditions affect not only biomass productivity but the dynamics of the overall microbial community. This study characterizes a microalgae culture from an 80m² pilot-scale raceway reactor fed with untreated urban wastewater. Operational conditions such as pH, dissolved oxygen, and culture height were varied to assess microbial population changes. Results demonstrate that increased culture height significantly promotes higher microalgal and bacterial diversity. pH, dissolved oxygen and culture height highly affects nitrifying bacteria activity and nitrogen accumulation. Furthermore, the system exhibited high disinfection capability with average LRVs of 3.36 for *E. coli* and 2.57 for *Clostridium perfringens*. Finally, the fungi species detected included *Chytridiomycota* and *Ascomycota*, while purple photosynthetic bacteria were also found in significant abundance within the medium.

1. Introduction

Climate change stands as one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century, impacting ecosystems, human health, and socio-economic systems worldwide. One critical effect of climate change is the intensification of water scarcity, posing threats to agriculture, industry, and human well-being (Rocha et al., 2022). Therefore, there is a growing concern to develop innovative solutions that address both climate change and challenges related to water reuse. In this context, biorefineries have emerged as innovative solutions to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, facilitating the transition to sustainable development and climate mitigation. Biorefineries are defined as the "sustainable processing of biomass into a spectrum of marketable products and energy" (de Jong and Jungmeier, 2015). Unlike traditional refineries, biorefineries operate with renewable feedstocks such as biomass. Additionally, the integration of water reuse technologies with biorefineries represents a unique opportunity to enhance resource efficiency and reduce environmental impact.

Microalgae biorefineries represent a significant opportunity for biomass production coupled with wastewater remediation (Fal et al., 2023). Coupling wastewater treatment to biomass production is well-suited for applications where achieving high purity in the final product is optional, such as bioenergy feedstocks. The lower purity of the final biomass is attributed to algae's coexistence with many microorganisms, predominantly bacteria, in wastewater media. Within these ecosystems, algae and bacteria engage in complex interactions, significantly influencing nutrient recovery efficiency and biomass productivity (Abdelfattah et al., 2023). Bacteria contribute substantially to system stabilization and enhance nutrient uptake efficiency, thereby positively impacting the overall efficiency of the microalgae production process (Wirth et al., 2020). For instance, the presence of bacteria reduces energy costs associated with system aeration to moderate excessive oxygen levels within the culture. Indeed, bacteria reduce the O₂ levels by consuming it during respiration while

releasing CO₂ necessary for microalgal growth. Therefore, bacteria additionally contribute to reducing the need for external CO₂ supply (González-González and De-Bashan, 2021).

A previous study conducted in Denmark revealed the presence of up to 3000 microbial species in a wastewater treatment plant utilizing genetic sequencing technology (Nierychlo et al., 2020). Nevertheless, only nitrifying, and heterotrophic bacteria have been identified to be in relevant abundance. Nitrifying bacteria consume ammonium (NH₄⁺) and release nitrite and nitrate (NO₂⁻/NO₃⁻) during nitrification, while heterotrophic bacteria are responsible for degrading organic matter and reducing chemical oxygen demand (COD) in wastewater (Oswald et al., 1953; Vargas et al., 2016). However, research interests have expanded beyond these bacterial populations, evaluating the presence of pathogenic bacteria (Lee et al., 2022), protozoa, fungi (Wang et al., 2023) as well as photosynthetic bacteria (Capson-Tojo et al., 2020). This expansion makes sense if considering the European Union's stringent regulation for water reuse (*Regulation 2020/741*, 2020) concerning the microbiological water quality. This regulation fixed a minimum reduction of indicator microorganisms such as *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) and *Clostridium perfringens* to ensure the safe use of reclaimed wastewater in agricultural irrigation. Consequently, monitoring these microorganisms is essential to further explore ways to maximize their reduction through optimal management of production systems. In addition, another class of photosynthetic organisms, mainly purple photosynthetic bacteria (PPB), recently attracted attention due to their potential in wastewater treatment and as a bioresource for high-value-added products (Lu et al., 2021). On the other hand, algae parasites can cause system damage in just a few days. Notably, fungi have been identified as one of the major contaminants in open systems (Carney et al., 2014), capable of germinating inside the algal cell wall (Laezza et al., 2022). Understanding the role of potential algae predators can help prevent their growth and

proliferation, thus stabilizing cultures and mitigating the risk of sudden damage to production systems.

The significance of microbial interactions in algal culture has become increasingly evident, to the extent that microalgal cultures are now being recognized as "holobionts" - encompassing not only microalgae but also all other microbial species that coexist with them (Calero and Nikel, 2019). This represents a paradigm shift in algal culture technology. Numerous studies have been dedicated to understanding microbial dynamics and interactions, both experimentally (Sánchez-Zurano et al., 2022) and through simulation methods (Nordio et al., 2024). Nevertheless, only a few studies have investigated the impact of microbes on microalgal productivity. Taxonomic composition and dynamics of microbes affect productivity in microalgal cultures, and disturbances in these microbiomes can hinder microalgal growth (Ramanan et al., 2016; Zengler and Zaramela, 2018). This supports the notion that the microbe's role can be as crucial as that of the microalgae itself.

In this regard, previous studies have mainly been carried out in laboratory scale. For instance, Ferro et al. evaluated microbial community dynamics through DNA metarecording of an 800L photobioreactor fed with untreated wastewater and illuminated with artificial light over an 8-month period. This study revealed a significant influence of light intensity, dissolved oxygen (DO), and pH on population diversity, particularly considering microalgae strains and bacterial species. However, the study did not delve into the dynamics of specific microbial species, instead providing a more generalized evaluation of algae and bacteria diversity (Ferro et al., 2020). In addition, there are few evaluations of microbial communities in large-scale outdoor production systems in the literature, mainly assessing the impact of the medium utilized (Clagnan et al., 2022; Erkelens et al., 2014) or the reactor designs (Clagnan et al., 2023). Nevertheless, a significant knowledge gap persists regarding the impact of operational variables, pH, culture height, and oxygen concentration on microbial

activity in pilot-scale systems. Therefore, addressing population changes and dynamics as a function of raceway reactor operation is especially relevant for providing precise guidance on managing production culture effectively.

This study aims to assess the dynamics and evolution of microorganism populations coexisting in a pilot-scale raceway reactor fed with urban wastewater. Specifically, the objective was to evaluate how the population evolved with changes in the raceway operations, focusing on pH, DO, and cultivation height. To this end, various control strategies for pH/DO were applied (Nordio et al., 2023). Three culture heights were also tested (8, 15, 22 cm). For each condition, samples were analysed for eukaryotic and prokaryotic abundance using next-generation sequencing (NGS), as well as for pathogenic bacteria using filtration techniques. Furthermore, the evaluation focused on specific microorganism dynamics, including algae strains, nitrifying bacteria, pathogens, PPB, and fungi. In conclusion, changes in the population were observed in the raceway in response to the applied variations and this study provides valuable insights into which operational conditions mainly affect them.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Raceway reactor

Samples were collected from a 12 m³ (80 m²) raceway reactor operated in semi-continuous mode between May and August with a fixed dilution rate of 0.2 day⁻¹ (Morillas-España et al., 2020). The raceway reactor is located in the SABANA demo plant (IFAPA research centre, La Cañada, Almeria). It is composed of a double channel of 40 m and a sump of 0.59 m³ for the gas injections through diffusers and an electric motor connected to a blade system for culture recirculation. pH is monitored through sensors and controlled through CO₂ injection in the reactor sump; additionally, an independent air flow is permitted to reduce the dissolved oxygen concentration. To check the culture state thoroughly, additional sensors were

installed to monitor the dissolved oxygen (0-400% Sat), temperature (0-80°C), and culture depth (4-40 cm). Moreover, meteorological stations allowed for registering the environmental conditions (solar radiation and environmental temperature).

2.2. Culture conditions

The chosen inoculum was *Scenedemus sp.* due to its capacity to grow easily in wastewater under a wide range of conditions (Fernández Sevilla et al., 2006). The strain was first to let growth with fertilizer medium (0.9 g·L⁻¹ of NaNO₃, 0.18 g·L⁻¹ of MgSO₄, 0.14 g·L⁻¹ of KH₂PO₄ and 0.03 g·L⁻¹ of a solid commercial mixture of micronutrients such as boron, copper, iron, manganese, molybdenum, and zinc; Kenogard, Spain) in columns of 3 m³ and then in a tubular system of 3000 m³ until it reached a concentration of 1 g·L⁻¹ and passed to raceway. The system was filled with primary wastewater until 15-cm height. The culture was operated in batch mode for 8 days, and then in continuous mode. The experiments began once the steady state was reached.

2.3. Wastewater characterization

The culture medium was urban wastewater collected from the University of Almeria. The wastewater was stored into a tank in the dark and filtered with a 200-µm industrial filter before entering the reactor. Actual wastewater is subjected to daily fluctuations in its composition. Concentrations varied between 10 and 250 mg·L⁻¹, 0 and 20 mg·L⁻¹, 10 and 90 mg·L⁻¹, and 200 and 500 mg·L⁻¹ for NH₄⁺, for NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, and COD, respectively. Precise water composition for each experiment can be find in in Supplementary material (S3).

2.4. Experimental design and sampling campaign

During this study, three operational variables were manipulated: pH, DO, and culture height. To achieve this, the system underwent four distinct control strategies and three variations in

culture height. Different pH/DO control strategies (On-off, PI, Event-based, and No control) were applied to the reactor based on a previous study (Nordio et al., 2023), maintaining the culture depth at 0.15 m. These approaches are described in detail therein. Set points for pH were established considering the optimal parameter value for the selected strain and set to 8 (Sánchez Zurano et al., 2021). Different culture depths were also tested (22 cm, 15 cm, and 8 cm) keeping the pH control strategy in On-off mode. Each condition was applied until the total volume of the system was replaced (at least) twice, with sample analysis carried out at the end of each treatment.

2.5. Biomass concentration and analytical measurements

Biomass concentration was measured daily through the dry weight technic. The culture was collected in the morning after the reactor sump, and 100mL were filtered through a 0.5- μm filter and dried for 24h at 80°C in an oven. The water obtained by the filtration and inlet wastewater was analysed in terms of nutrients (N-NO_2^- , NO_3^- , NH_4^+). Colorimetric techniques were used to determine nutrient concentration utilizing a spectrophotometer according to standard procedures (Standard IC 74246, Standard IC 38364, Standard IC 59755), while N-NO_2^- was measured with Hach-Lange kits (LCK-342).

Biomass productivity was calculated as follows in $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (1):

$$P_b = C_b * D * h \quad (1)$$

Where C_b is the biomass concentration in $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, D is the dilution rate in day^{-1} , and h is the culture height in cm.

2.6. Samples collection and DNA extraction

5-L culture was collected and centrifugated at 7.500 rpm to remove the liquid phase and keep the biomass. The biomass was immediately frozen and lyophilized. DNA was extracted using the DNeasy Plant® Kit (Qiagen, Germany). Yield and purity of the DNA extractions

was quantified in a Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) while eventual fragmentation was determined through gel electrophoresis on 1 % (w/v) 1 × TAE agarose gels. DNA was stored at -80 °C until analyses. DNA extractions were performed in triplicate.

2.7. Community structure by next generation sequencing (NGS)

The Illumina sequencing was performed on each DNA extraction. For bacterial analysis, the 16S rRNA gene's V3-V4 hypervariable region was specifically targeted and amplified using the Bakt_341F (CCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG) and Bakt_785R primers (GACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC) (Herlemann et al., 2011). Conversely, for eukaryotic examination, the V9 region of the 18S rRNA gene was amplified using the primers 1389F (TTGTACACACCGCCC) and 1510R (CCTTCYGCAGGTTACCTAC) (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2009). For fungal characterisation, the LSU D1 region of rRNA gene was amplified using the primers ITS4ngsF (GCATATCAATAAGCGSAGGAA) and LF402R (TTCCCTTTYARCAATTTTAC) (Ilicic et al., 2022).

The DNA libraries were subsequently sequenced utilizing the MiSeq Reagent Kit Nano on the Illumina MiSeq platform at Stab Vida Lda (Lisbon, Portugal). The resulting nucleotide sequences have been deposited in the NCBI SRA repository under the BioProject accession number PRJNA1063730. These sequences underwent quality assessment using FastQC software and were analyzed with DADA2. Truncation of reads was implemented at 220 (forward) and 200 (reverse) for 18S, and at 280 and 245 for 16S. Taxonomic assignment for prokaryotes utilized the SILVA database, while eukaryotic classification employed the Blastn algorithm against the NCBI nucleotide database, with taxonomy retrieved from the Taxdump Repository. All statistical analyses were performed on R studio (version 4.1.2) as in Clagnan et al., 2022. The prokaryotic pathway of the enzyme profile for N metabolism was investigated through iVikodak (Nagpal et al., 2019).

2.8. Screening of pathogens

Naturally occurring *E. coli*, total coliforms, and *Clostridium perfringens* were quantified using the membrane filtration technique with a detection limit of 1 CFU·100 mL⁻¹ mL. Inlet and outlet samples were filtered in duplicate throughout cellulose nitrate membrane filters (0.45 µm) and transferred to Petri dishes with the appropriate growth medium. Chromocult ® Coliform Agar (Millipore ®) was used for the detection and enumeration of *E. coli* and other coliform bacteria (*ISO 9308-1: Water Quality – Detection and enumeration of Escherichia coli and coliform bacteria – Part 1: Membrane filtration method.*, 2014). Petri dishes were incubated at 36 ± 2 °C for 21-24 h. Deep blue to violet colonies were enumerated as *E. coli* and salmon-rose to red colonies as other coliform bacteria. Total coliform indicator was the result of the sum of both *E. coli* and other coliform bacteria. As for *Clostridium perfringens*, m-CP Agar Base (Scharlau) prepared with m-CP Selective Supplement (Scharlau) was used (*ISO 14189: 2013. Water Quality – Enumeration of Clostridium perfringens – Method using membrane filtration.*, 2013). Plates were incubated at 44 ± 1 °C for 21 ± 3 h and yellow colonies turning to pink or red under ammonium hydroxide vapours were enumerated as *Clostridium perfringens*.

The Log Reduction Value (LRV) have been calculated as (2):

$$LRV = -\log_{10}\left(\frac{X_{in}}{X_{out}}\right) \quad (2)$$

Where X_i is CFU·100 mL⁻¹ mL inlet and outlet the raceway reactor (in the wastewater medium and in the reactor water after the separation of the biomass).

2.9. Statistical analysis

Data were analysed using analysis of variance ANOVA with STATGRAPHICS Centurion 19.

The criterion for statistical significance was $p < 0.05$. The results are expressed as mean values of three independent determinations ± standard deviations.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Influence of the operational conditions on biomass productivity

Since raceway reactors are outdoor facilities, solar radiation and environmental temperature are the variables most influencing microalgal productivity. Experiments were carried out during two distinct periods: the first, lasting one month (between May and June), had constant average PAR irradiance and environmental temperature of $1400 \pm 400 \mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ and $27 \pm 4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The second period, between July and August, had an average PAR of $1100 \pm 400 \mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$, while the average environmental temperature was $32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (S1). Since these values remained constant on average during the experimental trial, they can be considered as not directly influencing the variations observed in biomass productivity. Instead, these variations can be linked to the manipulation of each operational variable in the specific experiment.

Productivity is influenced by operational variables such as pH, DO, and culture height, and their control at optimal values. It is noteworthy that optimal pH control can be achieved through on-demand CO_2 injections, compensating for the inorganic carbon reduction in the system due to its uptake during photosynthesis. Simultaneously, high concentrations of DO, which can be inhibitory for microalgae, can be reduced by injecting compressed air into the reactor sump. Following this concept, various types of controllers can be designed. In the initial experimental set, the On-off, PI, Event-based, and no control of pH were tested. Briefly, On-off is a simple controller that switches between two variables (on and off), while PI and Event-based are continuous controllers (Nordio et al., 2023). In all experiments, pH was prioritized over DO, meaning that air was injected into the sump only when the pH fell below the set point (S2). Figure 1A illustrates biomass concentration, while Figure 1B depicts average values of pH and DO for each experiment. In Figure 1B, it is evident that the control strategies effectively maintained a constant pH of 8, while it was possible to reduce the DO concentration to 220% only with the implementation of the Event-based

strategy. Moreover, the consequences of lacking pH control within the system were assessed. This resulted in an uncontrolled pH increase to 10 and a reduction in DO levels to 160%. This unregulated condition had a direct impact on biomass productivity, as evidenced by the lowest recorded productivity observed without pH control, approximately $23 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. Conversely, a slight increase was registered with PI and On-off strategies ($25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$); while the highest productivity was achieved with the Event-based control strategy ($26 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$), demonstrating its superior ability to remove oxygen compared to other control strategies (Figure 1A).

Regarding the manipulation of the culture height, Figures 1D and 1C represent the average pH and DO registered, and the biomass productivity, respectively. In this case, the pH was controlled at 8 using an On-off strategy, while the dissolved oxygen concentration was effectively reduced to 150-180% (Figure 1D).

In Figure 1C an increase in biomass concentration (in $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) was observed along with the reduction of the culture height, ranging from $0.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ at 22 cm to $1.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ at 8 cm. These results align with findings in the literature, which suggest the possibility of increasing biomass concentration through the reduction of the culture's dark zone, known to be photosynthetically inactive due to an auto-shading effect (Morillas-España et al., 2020). However, biomass productivity did not follow the same trend. The highest biomass productivity of $28 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ was achieved with the culture height maintained at 15 cm. In comparison, there was a slight reduction at 22 cm, with productivity equal to $26 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, while there was a substantial drop when the culture height was kept at 8 cm ($16 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$). This outcome can be clarified by considering that productivity, expressed as $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, represents the net biomass quantity produced per day per square meter of utilized land. Consequently, it is calculated as the product of biomass concentration, dilution rate, and culture height (1). Since the dilution rate have been maintained constant for all the experiments (equal to 0.2 day^{-1}), at 8 cm, the reduction of the net daily harvesting grams

was not sufficiently compensated by the higher biomass concentration, resulting on a decrease in the productivity. From this perspective, it is conceivable that similarly, the quantity of nutrients per square meter is also diminished when excessively reducing the culture height while maintaining a constant dilution rate. This likely contributes to the drop in productivity under such conditions.

Therefore, it has been demonstrated that optimal conditions for operating the raceway reactor, resulting in higher biomass productivity, can be achieved by effectively controlling the pH and reducing dissolved oxygen through an Event-based strategy, with the optimal culture height set at 15 cm.

3.2. Microalgae strains

One of the primary challenges in outdoor microalgal production is establishing monoculture conditions. In open systems, the prevalence of contamination from the initial strain often leads to the generation of mixed cultures. The difficulty in achieving monoculture conditions in outdoor microalgal production arises from the adaptability of various microalgal species to similar environmental parameters, such as solar radiation, temperature, and pH (Brindhadevi et al., 2021). Conversely, seasonal fluctuations may prompt the replacement of initially cultivated algae with strains better suited to the prevailing production conditions. Monoculture production becomes achievable under extreme operational conditions that restrict the proliferation of competing contaminants. This is the case of *Spirulina* that is conventionally produced in alkaline environments (Ogbonda et al., 2007). Nevertheless, in the context of wastewater treatment, the establishment of a monoculture becomes less relevant, given the comparable nutrient uptake yield for N and P among various algal species (Procházková et al., 2014). Consequently, treatment facilities employing this methodology generally refrain from inoculating the reactors with a singular strain. Instead, they initially operate in batch mode until the algal species most resilient to the specific water composition and environmental conditions where the treatment site is located.

Figure 2 depicts the relative abundance of eukaryotes species detected in the culture during both experimental periods. In the initial experimental set, the system was successfully maintained close to monoculture conditions, with the predominant strain being *Desmodesmus armatus*. A noteworthy abundance of *Brachionus calyciflorus*, a rotifer commonly found in freshwater environments, was also detected. In aquaculture, rotifers serve as a feed source for fish, and their growth is typically augmented by providing microalgae, considered a suitable nutrient source (Ferreira et al., 2009). Additionally, as the pH became uncontrolled and approached 10, other strains, such as *Mallomonas annulata*, a heterokont in the family *Mallomonadaceae*, began to appear, showing their ability to better adapt to these conditions, together with other eukaryotic bodies such as fungi as *Resinicium friable*. Therefore, according to these results, maintaining an adequate pH control not only enhances productivity but also promotes the growth of a specific strain and reduces the likelihood of contamination, especially by fungi and rotifers.

In the second experimental set, the culture exhibited the coexistence of various eukaryotic species. Specifically, at a depth of 22 cm, a notable proliferation of rotifers was observed, identified as *Adineta vaga*, *Fillina terminalis*, and *Lecane inermis*. Conversely, at the other two culture heights, microalgae such as *Desmodesmus* (*armatus*, *abundance*, and *sp.*) and *Oocystis sp.* began to grow, although the rotifer *Fillina terminalis* persisted in high abundance.

In fact, there is a notable variability in eukaryotic species across all experiments and at different culture heights. Through the analysis of diversity indices (S7.1), it is possible to observe that, although the overall observed richness was higher for the first experimental set, the Simpson and Evenness indices suggest that manipulating the pH/DO generated lower diversity (ranging between 0.8 and 0.96) (S7.1A), indicating dominance by a few eukaryotic species. On the contrary, when manipulating the culture height, these indices decreased between 0.68 and 0.76, meaning higher diversity within the analysed samples

(S7.1B). These differences between the two experiments can be attributed to the diverse environmental conditions under which they were conducted, characterized by diverse temperatures. Furthermore, alterations in culture height substantially affect light penetration, along with changes in the net influx of water and nutrients into the reactor. Additionally, it is crucial to recognize the inherent challenges in controlling both periodic and diurnal variations that may arise in wastewater, adding an extra layer of complexity to the experimental conditions and the control of a specific microalgal strain.

3.3. Bacteria population

The following section outlines the findings from the 16S metagenomic analysis, elucidating the composition of bacterial populations within the examined samples. *Proteobacteria*, a group of CO oxidizer, emerged as one of the most relevant phyla, responding to the elevated concentrations of both inorganic and organic carbon in the medium. On the contrary, when changing the culture height, *Verrucomibiocota* increased its abundance between 0.1 and 0.5. This phylum, often classified as a "superphylum," encompasses numerous microorganisms commonly found in soil samples. Other noteworthy populations detected include *Planctomycetota*, widely distributed and integral to the carbon and nitrogen cycles, (including of Ammonium Oxidizing bacteria (AOB)), *Firmicutes* and *Bacteroidota* (generally found in the human intestine) (S4).

The richness indices ranged between 500 and 745 (corresponding to the experiment conducted at a 22 cm) (S7.2A). Additionally, the Simpson's index was approximately 0.98 for all samples analysed in the first experiment, signifying low diversity and the dominance of only a few bacterial species. In contrast, this index consistently decreased with changes in culture height (0.77 at 22 cm, 0.58 at 15 cm, and 0.53 at 8 cm), indicating the significant influence of this variable on the diversity of species within the culture (S7.2B).

In the next section, focus will be directed towards specific bacterial groups, including nitrifying bacteria, PPB, and pathogenic bacteria such as *E. coli*, total coliforms, and

Clostridium perfringens. The main objective was to comprehend how the environmental and operational conditions within the reactor influenced their growth and the overall recovery of nutrients and water disinfection.

3.3.1. Nitrifying bacteria

Nitrifiers are a group of autotrophic bacteria that perform nitrification in the presence of DO, playing a central role in the terrestrial nitrogen cycle (Prosser, 1990). In the framework of wastewater treatment, this bacterial group is highly relevant when the medium presents a significant concentration of NH_4^+ to be processed. Specifically, AOB are able to convert the most reduced form of nitrogen, NH_4^+ , into NO_2^- , while nitrate-oxidizing bacteria (NOB) are the responsible for the transformation of NO_2^- into NO_3^- . AOB and NOB constitute the family of *Nitrobacteraceae*, with AOB mainly classified with the genera *Nitrosomonas*, *Nitrosococcus*, *Nitrosospira*, *Nitrosolobus* *Nitrosovibrio*, while NOB *Nitrobacter*, *Nitrococcus*, *Nitrospira* and *Nitrospina*.

Complex interactions can occur between AOB, NOB, and microalgae. Algae need N to produce proteins, and they can assimilate it in the form of NH_4^+ or $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$. However, ammonium is their favourite N form, since it required less energy for assimilation, while the oxidized forms will be consumed only when NH_4^+ concentration in the medium is sufficiently low (Wu et al., 2013). In wastewater systems, microalgae compete with nitrifiers, particularly with AOB, for the consumption of ammonium. Furthermore, the accumulation of nitrite can be considered as a significant challenge in the management of algae-based wastewater systems. The excessive buildup of nitrate or nitrite can be detrimental, especially considering wastewater discharge regulations that impose limits on nitrogen levels, set at $15 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ from the European Union (*Council directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban waste water treatment*, 1991). Additionally, some researchers suggest that NO_2^- may adversely affect algae's photosynthetic activity, potentially causing damage to the photosynthetic apparatus (Aparicio et al., 2022). Consequently, comprehending the interaction between

microalgae and nitrifying bacteria, particularly AOB, is essential for the optimal management of production systems, the efficient removal of ammonium from the medium and prevent the accumulation of $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$.

Figure 3 illustrates the percentage of *Nitrobacteraceae* measured through NSG in the cultures during the experimental campaign, along with NH_4^+ removal and $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$ generation rates expressed in $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. The most relevant genus detected were *MND1*, *Ellin6067*, *oc32* and *Nitrosomonas*. Figure 3A presents the results from the first set of experiments involving the pH/DO control system, while Figure 3B depicts the second set where the culture height was changed.

An increase in nitrifying activity is noticeable when employing Even-based or no pH control, while lower concentrations were observed for On-Off and PI control strategies. Moreover, the overall system consumption of NH_4^+ was recorded between 3 and $4.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, while the generation of $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$ lied between 0.5 and $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. These trends can be elucidated by examining recorded pH and dissolved oxygen values in the medium for each case. In the latter two strategies, DO reached high concentrations because the injected air was insufficient to remove it effectively. Conversely, in the Event-based strategy, removal was improved while maintaining the pH at 8. Oxygen plays a fundamental role in the activity of these microorganisms as it is essential for the oxidation process during nitrification (Park and Noguera, 2004). When microalgae activity is low, nitrification does not occur due to insufficient oxygen availability. Conversely, when microalgae activity is high, complete nitrification can be achieved, limiting the formation of NO_2^- . However, beyond a certain concentration, their inhibition may occur, as supported by previous studies (Sánchez-Zurano et al., 2022). Therefore, it is possible to hypothesize that when the On-Off and PI strategies were employed, nitrification activity was inhibited due to the high concentration of oxygen. In contrast, with the Event-based strategy, the oxygen level was effectively reduced, favouring their proliferation. Additionally, a higher percentage was recorded when no pH

control was employed. In this case, the reduced level of dissolved oxygen and the higher pH values favoured the grow of these microorganisms.

Regarding the second set of experiments, it is evident a trend of an increase in the percentage of nitrifiers with the increase in culture height. Furthermore, it was observed that the NH_4^+ uptake improved significantly, reaching up to $4.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, accompanied by an accumulation of generated $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^-$ up to 2.5 and $0.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ respectively. These concentrations can be explained by the increased activity of nitrifiers, which consume ammonium in substantial amounts, producing nitrate and nitrite that accumulate due to the reduced activity of microalgae. The last one has been demonstrated to be a potential photosynthetic inhibitor (González-Camejo et al., 2020). As the culture height increases, a larger dark zone is formed due to self-shading, with only the first 3 cm of the culture being photosynthetically active (Morillas-España et al., 2021). This leads to diminished photosynthetic capacity and algal grow, favouring the proliferation of the bacterial population. Additionally, it has been reported that light penetration influences the activity of nitrifiers, and excessive light can negatively impact their growth and activity (González-Camejo et al., 2022). This finding potentially explains the low concentration detected at 8 cm.

A functional analysis, based on the 16S rRNA gene, was further conducted to investigate the bacterial enzymatic profile for N-metabolism (KEGG pathway: map00910) using iVikodak (Table 1, S5). In examining the primary pathways of N-cycling (including nitrification, denitrification, assimilatory, and dissimilatory nitrate reduction), the no control and Event-based pH controlling strategies exhibited higher potential ($p < 0.05$) for nitrification, while the On-off control showed the lowest potential ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the uncontrolled pH demonstrated a higher potential for the other pathways, with the On-Off control exhibiting lower potential, and the PI control showing intermediate potential. No significant differences across all treatments were observed for assimilatory nitrate reduction. Interestingly, the

Event-based displayed the highest variability, being high in nitrification potential while low in dissimilatory nitrate reduction. When considering the three different heights, nitrification exhibited the highest potential at 15 cm compared to 8 cm ($p < 0.05$), with no significant difference observed between 22 cm and the other two heights. Denitrification and dissimilatory nitrate reduction followed a similar trend, with the highest potential at 22 cm, intermediate at 15 cm, and the lowest at 8 cm ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, assimilatory nitrate reduction showed the lowest value at 22 cm rather than at 8 cm.

3.3.2. Pathogenic bacteria

In June 2023, the European Union issued a more restrictive regulation specifying the minimum requirements for water reuse in agricultural irrigation (*Regulation 2020/741*, 2020). This document includes specifications concerning the frequency of water analysis monitoring, user points for irrigation and sets different water quality classes regarding the *E. coli* concentration. Specifically, the regulation comes more restrictive regarding the reduction of this pathogen as, for example, the water class A require a reduction of 10 CFU (colony-forming unit)·mL⁻¹ (Truchado et al., 2021). Within this new legislative framework, the assessment of the disinfection capacity of microalgae systems becomes crucial, particularly concerning the presence and concentration of indicator microorganisms such as *E. coli* and *C. perfringens*. Figure 4 displays the inactivation profiles of these pathogenic bacteria monitored throughout the experimental trial, providing insights into the disinfection efficiency of the microalgae system.

Figure 4A illustrates that the control strategy had minimal influence on the *E. coli* inactivation profile. Notably, there was little variation in the influent total concentration of *E. coli*, except when no control strategy was employed, resulting in a 1 log-unit higher load into the reactor compared to other conditions. Taking this into consideration, the PI strategy demonstrated the highest LRV of 3.6, while employing the On-off control led to a lower LRV of 1.6.

Inactivation values for the Event-based and no-control strategies were comparable. Regardless of the control strategy, these significant reductions can primarily be attributed to *E. Coli*'s vulnerability to solar radiation, enhanced by the synergistic impact of pH and DO, given its gram-negative nature (Ruas et al., 2020). Several research studies have consistently shown that maintaining a pH above 8.5 significantly enhances the removal of *E. coli*. Elevated pH levels not only improve photon absorption but also enhance photooxidation. This observation is consistent with the pH values documented in this study (Figure 4A). However, the sunlight exposure accounts for over 80% of *E. coli* inactivation, making it the most influential factor (Chambonniere et al., 2023; Craggs et al., 2004). Additionally, the extended hydraulic residence times (over 5 days) further contribute to prolonged sunlight exposure, resulting in more efficient removal.

A slight effect of the culture height was observed on *E. coli* inactivation (Figure 4B). Comparable LRVs were achieved for heights of 15 cm and 22 cm (4.7 and 4.9 LRV, respectively). However, the inlet total load concentrations were also similar. Surprisingly, only a slight reduction (3.5 LRV) was achieved when operating the photoreactor at an 8 cm. Typically, a greater reduction would be expected at a lower culture height, as a shorter light optical path favours the inactivation of pathogenic microorganisms. However, this result is likely due to the 1 log-unit lower *E. coli* inlet load compared to the other cases tested, highlighting the impact of the variability in wastewater effluent physicochemical and microbiological composition (Belachqer-El Attar S. et al., 2023). The *E. coli* LRVs achieved in this study were comparable to those reported elsewhere, despite the application of different environmental and operating conditions. (Chambonniere et al., 2021; Ruas et al., 2020, 2018).

Regarding *Clostridium perfringens* inactivation profiles, no influence of operational variables was observed (Figure 4C,D). Additionally, there was no significant variation in inlet total load

concentrations. Comparable LRVs were achieved across different control methods: 1.8, 1.8, 2.2, and 2.3 for On-Off, PI, Event-based, and no control, respectively (Figure 4C). Similarly, its inactivation was not affected by culture height (Figure 4D) (LRV equal to 3.3, 3.5, and 3.1 for 8, 15, and 22 cm, respectively), despite a 1 log-unit difference in inlet concentrations when operating at a 22-cm culture height compared to the other heights studied. Notably, the reductions obtained in the second experimental set were higher than those in the first, as the inlet load was 2 log-units higher.

In contrast to *E. coli*, *Clostridium perfringens* is a spore-forming gram-positive bacterium highly resistant to disinfection treatments such as photocatalysis, solar disinfection (SODIS) (García-Prieto et al., 2022; Lanao et al., 2010), and chlorination processes (Pichel et al., 2023). This resistance is likely due to its capacity for spore-forming under adverse external conditions (Gutiérrez-Alfaro et al., 2018; Ruas et al., 2023). Although the sporulation phenomenon occurs in a temperature range between 75 and 80 °C, which cannot be reached in the photobioreactor, exposure to solar radiation remains the primary factor promoting it (Gutiérrez-Alfaro et al., 2018). In addition, oxygen is a significant stress factor for *Clostridium perfringens* since it is an anaerobic bacterium (Morvan et al., 2021). Hence, its inactivation is likely attributed to the elevated DO concentrations reached in the culture. (Bongiorno et al., 2020). However, the effect of DO alone is inefficient. Yet, when combined with sunlight, the inactivation is enhanced due to the formation of toxic reactive oxygen species such as singlet oxygen and peroxides. (Pompei et al., 2023). In the literature, different LRVs for *Clostridium perfringens* have been reported, depending on the operational conditions applied. For instance, in a study conducted by Ruas et al. in 2023, a system with a surface area of 0.32 m² and a Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) of 6 days achieved a minimum reduction of only 0.3, while the maximum LRV (2.6) was attained with a system of 0.13 m² and an HRT of 5 days (Ruas et al., 2020). These values were comparatively lower

than those obtained in this study. However, it's important to note that these experiments were conducted at a laboratory scale, utilizing lower HRTs and consequently shorter exposure to light time. Additionally, radiation and DO concentrations were considerably lower in those experiments (Ruas et al., 2023, 2018).

The inactivation profile of total coliforms (Figure 4E) indicates that control strategies have minimal impact on them, resulting in lower LRVs. In some cases, outlet concentrations even surpassed those at the inlet. This outcome can be attributed to total coliforms being gram-negative non-endospore-forming bacteria, which include both faecal and non-faecal coliforms, making them challenging to differentiate (Okafor et al., 2020). Among coliform bacteria, especially *E. coli*, faecal coliforms serve as a more precise indicator of faecal contamination compared to other coliform groups. Therefore, while several coliform bacteria are naturally present and generally pose no public health risk, *E. coli* specifically signals potential contamination concerns (Brackett, 1993). As a result, total coliforms are not designated as indicator microorganisms in the EU 2020/741 regulation (Regulation 2020/741, 2020).

Furthermore, no significant effect of culture height was observed (Figure 4F), and LRVs were similar when operating at culture heights of 15 and 22 cm (2.6 and 2.4 LRV, respectively), whereas only a reduction of 0.8 log-units was obtained for 8 cm. This outcome contrasts with expectations, as lower culture heights typically result in a lower light optical path and, consequently, higher removal. However, this discrepancy can be attributed to the lower inlet concentration during this experiment.

Similar to *E. coli*, total coliforms are significantly affected by solar radiation, pH, and DO as gram-negative bacteria. The reduction values obtained were favourable and comparable to those determined in previous studies. (Chambonniere et al., 2021).

In summary, sunlight-mediated pathogen inactivation is likely enhanced by high pH and DO concentrations working synergistically (Chambonniere et al., 2021). The removal of *E. coli* and faecal total coliforms from wastewater in raceway reactors primarily depends on solar radiation, with pH and DO also playing significant roles. In contrast, the inactivation of *Clostridium perfringens* is mainly attributed to high DO concentration combined with solar radiation. Endogenous and exogenous photooxidation both increase with rising DO concentration, while exogenous photooxidation rises with elevated pH levels. Consequently, high DO concentrations facilitate increased oxygen transfer through cell membranes, promoting the formation of reactive oxidative species both inside and outside the cells. Simultaneously, high pH increases the susceptibility of cell membranes to damage, thereby enhancing the action of exogenous reactive oxidative species. This oxidative stress in microorganism cells damages the central dogma of microbial DNA replication, which is essential for their metabolic growth (Chambonniere et al., 2021).

As mentioned earlier, the results are consistent with findings in the literature and sometimes even exceed them, depending on the raceway reactor and operational conditions employed (Ruas et al., 2020, 2018). Consequently, this study emphasizes the remarkable efficacy of microalgae raceway technology in pathogen removal, offering a promising alternative to conventional secondary treatments for generating high-quality reclaimed water. Nevertheless, additional treatment is necessary to ensure its safe utilization in agricultural irrigation.

3.3.3. Purple phototropic bacteria

PPB are a group of photosynthetic bacteria that have gained significant attention in the field of wastewater treatment due to their notable carbon capture capacity and resilience to pollutants, salinity, and low temperatures (Sepúlveda-Muñoz et al., 2022). While the development of this technology in wastewater treatment is still in its early stages, several

studies demonstrate its potential, yielding promising results across different types of waters (Hülse et al., 2014; Madukasi et al., 2010). These bacteria possess advantageous characteristics, especially high metabolic flexibility, including the ability to grow both chemotrophically and phototrophically under anoxic conditions and utilise the near-infrared electromagnetic spectrum. This capability is facilitated by bacteriochlorophyll pigments, giving them a distinctive colour ranging from orange to purple (Sepúlveda-Muñoz et al., 2022). Within the category of PPB, two distinct groups can be identified: purple sulfur bacteria (PSB) and purple non-sulfur bacteria (PNSB), which often coexist in the same environment (Capson-Tojo et al., 2020). The first group, belonging to the *Chromatiaceae* family, engages in anoxygenic photosynthesis, utilizing sulfur compounds instead of water as electron donors. They oxidize hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) or elemental sulfur (S) to form elemental sulfur or sulfate, releasing electrons in the process (Madigan and Jung, 2009). On the other hand, purple non-sulfur bacteria include *Comamonadaceae*, *Rhodocyclaceae*, *Rhodobacteraceae*, and *Acetobacteraceae*, among others. On the same way as PSB, they conduct anoxygenic photosynthesis using bacteriochlorophyll pigments, but utilizing nitrogen as a source of energy for their growth, although their nitrogen fixation ability is not yet fully evaluated (Higuchi-Takeuchi and Numata, 2019).

Figure 5 illustrates the relative abundance (%) of PSB (Figure 5 A,B) and PNSB (Figure 5 C,D). Regarding the first bacterial group, they were detected in low concentrations, ranging from 0.2 to 2% and 0.1 to 0.35% for the first and second experimental sets, respectively. No clear trend correlating the implemented strategy with the variation in PSB concentration was observed. Conversely, PNSB were detected in higher concentrations, varying between 8 and 11% (Figure 5C, D). Specifically, the abundance remained similar during all control strategies implemented, while a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) was observed when no pH control strategy was implemented (Figure 5C). Moreover, regarding the abundance of PNSB

with changing culture height, it was observed a trend where their concentration increases accordingly (11% at 22 cm, 5% at 15 cm, and 2% at 8 cm).

The presence of these bacteria can be explained by analysing the operational variables and the composition of the wastewater. Although recent research has explored the possibility of deploying mixed cultures of microalgae and purple bacteria to enhance nutrient uptake efficiency in wastewater (Shen et al., 2022), it has been demonstrated that high concentrations of DO can be detrimental for the growth of these bacteria. Photosynthetic bacteria conduct photosynthesis under anoxic conditions, and high concentrations of dissolved oxygen ($> 4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) can decrease the growth rate of PPB, potentially leading to pigment loss and decreased photosynthetic capability. However, despite reducing PPB growth rates under aerobic conditions, their aerobic heterotrophic capabilities offer some resilience by allowing them to grow via chemoheterotrophy as the dominant catabolic pathway instead of photoheterotrophy (Capson-Tojo et al., 2021). This doesn't imply microbial dominance, but it may enable their coexistence in reactors with microalgae. In microalgae-based systems, oxygen concentrations can reach values higher than $22 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, although during the night, this concentration can drop below $4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ due to respiration effects (S2). Therefore, it is hypothesised that the operational conditions may not favour their proliferation and growth. For this reason, the most promising outcomes in the framework of water remediation have been attained by employing sequential reactors for the separate cultivation of PPB and microalgae, as opposed to cultivating them together in a mixed culture. A study proposed by Sepúlveda-Muñoz et al., 2022, for instance, demonstrated the feasibility of achieving substantial carbon and nitrogen recovery (up to 92% and 86%, respectively) from piggery wastewater through the utilization of sequential reactors.

Hence, the presence of these bacteria in the culture can be plausibly attributed to their occurrence in the influent rather than proliferating into the reactor. This is supported by prior

analyses utilizing flow cytometry methods in the same medium, which indicated a notable presence of photosynthetic bacteria in the inflow. On the same time, this could potentially elucidate the elevated concentration observed with an increase in culture height. Both PSB and PNSB lower concentration at lower culture heights may be attributed to lower net inflow and harvesting while maintaining a fixed dilution rate of 0.2 day^{-1} . Moreover, concerning the first bacterial group, their lower concentration could potentially be related to the sulfur (S) concentration inside the culture medium. The literature reports that urban wastewater influent typically has a low S concentration ($10\text{-}20 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) (Tchobanoglous et al., 2003), which can increase due to human industrial activities (Lin et al., 2018). In this study, the wastewater is originated from a small community (University of Almeria), suggesting a reasonably low S concentration.

However, further research is needed to conduct comprehensive analyses of wastewater composition and microbial populations in the inflow to draw conclusive results. This could provide valuable insights for advancing the development of these systems and confirming the feasibility of creating co-cultures of algae and photosynthetic bacteria for wastewater treatment.

3.4. Fungi

Fungi are eukaryotic organisms that include yeasts, molds, and other forms, characterized by an internal cell structure and a cell wall. They are commonly found in aquatic environments, where they primarily decompose organic material, which is fundamental to their life cycle (Gessner et al., 2007). Fungal growth is influenced by various factors, such as light, temperature, pH, and nutrient availability. Specifically, the proliferation of fungi can be enhanced by specific nutrients such as magnesium, potassium, sulfate, and organic compounds like glucose or sucrose (Hoffman et al., 2008). Despite not being photosynthetic, fungi utilize light as a significant source of energy, enabling them to adapt to stressful conditions and effectively navigate the environment (Yu and Fischer, 2019). Consequently, in

wastewater systems related to microalgae cultivation, fungal populations hold great significance due to the abundant organic matter available and exposure to sunlight.

Fungi can interact with other microorganisms in various ways, but in the case of algae-bacteria cultures, the primary interaction is antagonism, as fungi compete with them for nutrient consumption (Baudy et al., 2021). However, other studies have demonstrated their synergy, which can enhance nutrient removal from wastewater (Jiang et al., 2019). In many cases, fungi have been considered as algae parasites, releasing a wide spectrum of metabolisms and chemical compounds such as mycotoxins and enzymes that affect microalgae cells (Laezza et al., 2022). Indeed, fungi can secrete specific enzymes damaging cell walls, allowing them to settle and germinate inside the host, resulting in a significant loss of the microalgae population in the production system. *Chytridiomycota* is the most common parasite associated with microalgae, typically causing biomass loss in outdoor cultivations. However, parasites are specific to each microalgae host. In the case of *Scenedemus sp.*, *Phlyctidium scenedesmi* (Chytrid), *Amoebophilidium protococcarum* (Aphelid), and *Rhizophidium sp.* (Carney et al., 2014; Letcher et al., 2013) have been reported as the most common parasites.

Figure 6 represents the major fungal phylum detected in the microalgae culture. During the first experimental period, the predominant fungal phylum was *Chytridiomycota*, with varying abundance in the culture between 0.75 and 0.1, depending on the applied operational conditions. Specifically, uncontrolled pH led to an increase in this parasite, while its abundance decreased improving the control. The main genera detected in these cases were *Rhizophydiales* and *Chytridium*, known as common algae predators (S7), particularly for *Scenedemus sp.*, the dominant microalgae species present in the reactor during this specific period (Figure 2). Additionally, another phylum detected was *Blastocladiomycota*, especially when implementing control strategies such as On-off and PI (S7). This phylum is reported

in the literature as another microalgae predator, particularly for *Hemacoccus Pluvialis* (Asatryan et al., 2019).

In the second experimental period, the abundance of *Chytridiomycota* became less relevant, while *Ascomycota* increased in abundance between 0.5 and 0.55. Additionally, a new phylum, *Basidiomycota*, along with *Blastocladiomycota*, was detected. *Ascomycota* and *Basidiomycota* are fungi commonly found in microalgae-based wastewater systems, and they have been suggested to interact synergistically with microalgae rather than acting solely as predators (Li et al., 2022). The reduction of *Chytridiomycota* during this experimental set can be explained by the decrease in abundance of its specific host, *Scenedesmus sp.*, which was replaced by other microalgae during this specific period.

Similarly observed in both eukaryotic and prokaryotic populations, although the overall observed richness was higher for the first experimental set (ranging between 94 and 190 for the first and 71 and 103 for the second) (S 7.3A), the Simpson and Evenness indices indicate that the diversity of fungal species was higher during the experiment where the culture height was changed (S 7.3B), particularly at 8 cm, where these indices reached 0.23. However, finding a correlation between operational conditions (pH, DO, and culture height) and specific fungi phyla or abundance was not possible. This accentuates the challenge related to the management of fungal contamination in outdoor microalgae production. Fungal dynamics in such systems are influenced by various factors, including nutrient availability, temperature fluctuations, and the specific microalgal community present. To address this challenge effectively, future research could delve deeper into understanding the interactions between operational variables and fungal populations. Additionally, exploring advanced monitoring techniques and implementing targeted strategies for fungal control could prove instrumental in maintaining the stability and productivity of outdoor microalgae cultivation systems.

4. Insights and future perspectives

The analyses performed on the microbiological dynamics within the raceway reactor have yielded valuable insights into the effects of operational variables:

- Controlling the pH to defined values brings several benefits, including: (i) increased productivity, (ii) reduction of nitrogen accumulation due to reduced activity of nitrifiers, (iii) promotion of growth in a specific algal strain, and (iv) decreased risk of fungal predator contamination.
- DO is a crucial parameter influencing algal productivity. The accumulation of DO can lead to the inhibition of algae together with nitrifying bacteria. Furthermore, results suggest that coupling PPB and microalgae production for wastewater treatment may be not feasible, especially in highly productive ponds. Concluding, it has been showed that it is necessary to strike a balance in DO concentration to favour microalgal activity over bacterial activity while simultaneously avoiding excessive nitrification, which can result in nitrogen accumulation. Finally, it has been shown that the production of oxygen by microalgae is beneficial in terms of reducing pathogens in the medium, particularly *Clostridium perfringens*.
- Culture height has been shown to have the most significant impact on microalgae, bacteria, and fungal diversity. While wastewater treatment plants typically prefer to employ a culture height of 30 cm to increase the amount of water treated per surface area utilized, it has been demonstrated that excessive increase in culture depth can lead to several disadvantages, including: (i) lower productivity, (ii) increased microalgal and bacterial diversity, and (iii) significant nitrogen accumulation and enhanced nitrification. On the other hand, culture height does not seem to have a relevant influence on pathogen deactivation.

For future studies, it would be advisable to standardize the microbiological monitoring campaign of cultivations, enabling a broader overview to evaluate the effects of various conditions and seasons over the year. Furthermore, future research should focus more on evaluating and monitoring pathogens and algae predators to reduce the risk of system damage and productivity loss.

In conclusion, the most productive and feasible approach appears to be implementing an Event-based strategy and cultivating at a depth of 15 cm. Under these conditions, the highest biomass productivity was achieved, with no significant nitrogen accumulation and lower concentrations of algae predators observed. However, these results are specific to the observations made in the particular system and raceway. Further research is necessary to confirm whether these findings are applicable to all production systems.

Conclusions

The study shows culture height significantly influences population dynamics, favouring diversity in microalgae and bacteria. pH and dissolved oxygen control impact especially on nitrifying bacteria activity, with oxygen being essential but inhibiting at high concentrations. At the same time, uncontrolled pH promotes nitrogen accumulation. *Chytridiomycota* and *Ascomycota* were prominent fungi, while purple non-sulfur bacteria were prevalent photosynthetic bacteria, affected by oxygen and culture height. Microalgae systems effectively disinfect pathogenic bacteria like *E. coli* (LRV 3.36) and *Clostridium perfringens* (RLV 2.57), likely due to light exposure and dissolved oxygen.

CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

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DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the H2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement (project: Digitalgaesation, 955520) and by the H2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme (projects: PRODIGIO, 101007006; REALM, 101060991). Also, this work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (project: HYCO2BIO, PID2020-112709RB-C21, TED2021-130458B-I00). All the authors would like to thank the Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training (IFAPA). S. Belachqer-El Attar thanks the PPIT-UAL for her predoctoral research contract (CPRE2023-007).

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Tables

Table 1. N-pathways abundance profile inferred by iVikodak

	pH control strategy				Height		
	On-off	PI	Event-based	No control	22 cm	15 cm	8 cm
Nitrification	1.51 ± 0.04 c	2.34 ± 0.02 b	2.84 ± 0.09 a	2.81 ± 0.04 a	3.09 ± 0.13 ab	3.12 ± 0.07 a	2.37 ± 0.22 b
Denitrification	3 ± 0.01 c	4.02 ± 0.01 b	4.08 ± 0.05 b	4.55 ± 0.02 a	4.72 ± 0.06 a	4.32 ± 0 b	3.22 ± 0.16 c
Assimilatory nitrate reduction	6.1 ± 0.13	5.39 ± 0.07	5.38 ± 0.06	6.09 ± 0.02	4.62 ± 0.04 c	5.03 ± 0.02 b	5.76 ± 0.15 a
Dissimilatory nitrate reduction	4.12 ± 0.05 bc	4.19 ± 0.08 b	3.86 ± 0 c	4.7 ± 0.03 a	5.23 ± 0.01 a	4.59 ± 0.04 b	4.31 ± 0.06 c
Others	85.26 ± 0.23 a	84.06 ± 0.18 b	83.84 ± 0.01 b	81.84 ± 0.08 c	82.33 ± 0.24 ab	82.93 ± 0 b	84.35 ± 0.46 a

Figures

Figure 1: Microalgal biomass productivity and average operational variables: A) average productivity [$\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$] and biomass concentration [$\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$] by changing pH/DO control strategies; B) pH and DO average values by changing pH/DO control strategies; C) average productivity [$\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$] and biomass concentration [$\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$] by changing culture height; d) pH and DO average values by changing the culture height.

Figure 2: Main eukaryotic species in the culture

Figure 3 Nitrobacteraceae % and NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , NO_2^- generation/removal in $[\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}]$: A) pH/DO control strategy experiment; B) culture height experiment.

Figure 4: CFU/100ml of pathogenic bacteria inlet outlet of the system and relative RLV; A) *E. Coli* pH/DO experiment; B) *E. Coli* culture height experiment; C) *Clostridium perfringens* pH/DO experiment; D) *Clostridium perfringens* culture height experiment; E) Total coliforms pH/DO experiment; F) Total Coliforms culture height experiment.

Figure 5: % of photosynthetic bacteria: A) Purple sulfur bacteria % during pH/DO experiment; B) Purple sulfur bacteria % during culture height experiment; C) Purple non-sulfur bacteria % during pH/DO experiment; D) Purple non-sulfur bacteria % during culture height experiment.

Figure 6: Main fungi phylum detected in the culture.